
Research on Visual Environmental Posters Creative Design

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Abstract The study adopts creative design through graphic visual posters, allowing students to demonstrate the outcomes of interactions between organisms and the environment using computer software applications. This aims to stimulate deeper reflections on environmental issues. Secondly, the teachers select exemplary works for display to raise awareness among individuals about the importance of ecological environment. These showcased works also serve as valuable resources for further research and as references for curriculum design.

Keywords Graphic Visualization, Ecological Environment, Creative Design, Visual Design.

Introduction

This paper utilizes graphic visual posters to present various scenarios resulting from human interactions within their environment. Through these visual concepts, it showcases the pollution and toxicity caused by human-environment relationships, aiming to raise awareness and consciousness about environmental protection.

The poster design incorporates various design elements representing interactions between different organisms and their environment, inspiring students to unleash their creativity. They are encouraged to derive visual elements from ecological substances, human forms, and other diverse entities to achieve the intended design objective of raising awareness.

2. Literature Review

Aesthetic principle not only concerns the perception of visual beauty, but most crucially, the cognitive-affective responses derived from experiencing such stimuli [3]. Academic journals are not known for the quality of their visual designs or the reading experiences they provide, despite being fundamental to the dissemination of research and knowledge in most disciplines [1]. This research outcome reveals that the visual layout and arrangement of journal magazines are crucial issues.

Companies are increasingly including innovative visual design elements such as animations and pictographs in digital communication [5]. There has paper proposes a graphic design layout method based on visual perception [4]. Secondly, That has study explores how recent design guidelines have focused on the visual variety of streetscapes making them more attractive [2]. This also highlights the importance of appropriate environmental visual design. Additionally, research has been conducted to design the visual aspects of intelligent traffic displays with the aim of proposing more user-friendly designs that better align with human needs and preferences [6].

3. Design Thinking

Humanity often sacrifices environmental conservation for its own interests, such as in the product design process, where the excessive use of raw materials leads to water and soil pollution. Similarly, the emphasis on attractiveness in packaging design can cause toxic pollution due to the overuse of pigments. Today, mankind has to contemplate what constitutes good design. Is the most valuable design the one that causes the least environmental pollution? Or is it something else?

Aspiring designers should shoulder the responsibility of environmental conservation, and it is crucial to strive towards the direction and goal of not allowing their design outcomes to cause environmental pollution. Design

education should also convey and teach students the responsibility of caring for the environment, cultivating the next generation of designers to work towards the creation of a zero-pollution environment.

4. Achievements Exhibition

The teacher and industry practitioner jointly formulated: (1) visual elements (30%); (2) creative expression (30%); (3) color scheme (30%); (4) design concept (10%) evaluation criteria, to provide a reference for the industry in their development of innovative products (figure 1).

Figure 1: Design results

5. Results and Contributions

Caring for the environment and conserving ecology have always been important topics in design education. Especially in recent years, with the urging and emphasis of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on

global sustainable practices, humanity can no longer ignore the repercussions of environmental degradation and ecological imbalance.

This paper integrates the concern of both teachers and students for environmental conservation into the creative design of visual posters, aiming to achieve a deeper understanding of the ecological environment and present a greater diversity of creative design elements. It serves as a positive value by raising awareness among all humanity about the importance of environmental protection and its impact.

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